

MEDICAL SCIENCES

CONTIGUOUS CLUSTER BOUNDARIES OF HELMINTHIASIS: INDIA GROUND LEVEL RESEARCH

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Abstract

To be precise, India being a tropical and endemic country at the high risk zone of Helminthiasis with warm and moist climate it supports and accelerates the survival and growth of parasitic eggs and larvae of helminth species. As per the statistics of WHO, India yields about 25% of the global cases [1]. To understand the prevalence and spatial distribution of Helminthiasis in several geographical sites of India I prepared a Questionnaire and distributed it for a comprehensive baseline census of individuals from various distinct sites of India. And also underwent meta-analysis of several systematic literature published based on the PRISMA guidelines and correlated it with the statistics provided by WHO [1]. The most common parasites were revealed to be *Ascaris lumbricoides*, *Ancylostoma duodenale* [hookworm] and *Trichuris trichiura* [whipworm]. Faecal-Oral route transmission itself reveals that the infection targets the developing countries with poor sanitation methods and socio-economic status. In India the highest prevalence was found in Tamil Nadu, Andhra Pradesh, Bihar, West Bengal and Assam and the lowest prevalence in Madhya Pradesh and the valleys of Kashmir [2]. The data provided by the census revealed that 53.5% of infections were caused by *A. lumbricoides* being the dominant species targeting the age group below 20 witnessing 60.3% cases from the rural areas. The survey also addresses that the infection targets the children belonging to the age group of 1-19 years. Though Indian government initiated a massive deworming program globally still it has accelerating cases of infection due to improper sanitation. Proper sanitation and hygiene practices should be established along with deworming medications biannually in order to drive the infectious rate down.

Keywords: Helminthiasis, Anthelmintics, deworming sanitation, Swachh Bharat, Anganwadi, endemic, Body Mass Index, globally, India.

Introduction

Since the last few decades, helminth infection has been an affliction to the human communities of tropical and sub-tropical region afflicting nearly 1 billion individuals globally as per the records provided by the WHO in 2020 [1]. The contagium in addition to impairing health it also hinders the cognitive and physical development of children exposed. Noticing the integral condition of this chronic infection WHO along with other organisations like The World bank, The United Nations, civil society and so on planned to reduce the impact of this spell with school level massive drug administration programs. A recent study computes that around 300 million people suffer from severe helminth infections and around 15,000 deaths annually [3]. In 2015, understanding the importance and necessity of deworming the endemic zones of the nation the Indian government obtaining the support from WHO launched

a huge deworming program targeting 241 million children who are at the risk of getting infected [4]. In the same year the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare (MoHFW) organised an expert team to enumerate the frequency and prevalence of STH in every geographical sites of India. They outlined 14 states with high, 19 states with moderate and 2 states with low prevalence of STH. After the analysis bi-annual deworming programs were suggested to every states and union territories except Rajasthan and Madhya Pradesh as they had the least prevalence ensuring that annual deworming would help in this case. The first National Deworming Day was observed on February 2015. In order to assess the scenario in detail I initiated a survey among 200 random individuals from different geographical sites of India by distributing Questionnaires in an online platform to understand how far does the infection invades

and to check the quality of awareness created among them by the government with the help of NDD.

Materials and Methods

I obtained the required information via Questionnaires, surveys, interviews and Published documents

and records. Primarily I revised many literature reviews which were analysed based on PRISMA guidelines targeting STH to understand the scenario in depth [1-10].

Figure 1. How literatures were selected to understand the sufficient knowledge.

After understanding the afflictions caused, I created a Questionnaire and circulated it to a total of 200 students of various geographical sites belonging to the age group of less than 21 through an online platform. This survey helped me to interpret and suggest the considerable improvements that can be made for the betterment of indigenous people from infection prone zone. I also made sure that the surveyed population is nutritionally healthy by calculating their Body Mass Index with the help of values [body mass divided by the square of height] provided during the survey.

In order to fulfil the study with updated scenario I interviewed few health care workers from primary health care centres of few endemic areas to drive a conclusion. Better observation is incomplete in the absence of statistical data, so required data were collected from WHO to compare the velocity of infection from the time period 2014-2020. With the aid of Microsoft Office software, I fed the collected data into it and used diagrammatic representation to meliorate the study further.

Figure 2: This stacked line chart represents the data aggregated regionally and globally.

Year	INDIA
2014	22,03,77,224
2015	22,38,56,719
2016	22,56,34,363
2017	22,56,34,363
2018	42,95,57,443
2019	43,56,38,057
2020	43,56,38,057

Figure 3: The number of cases in the past 7 years. It shows no visible deceleration due to reduced Sanitation in the endemic areas nowadays.

Figure 4: Geographical distribution of STH in India (2015) Statistics were collected from.

Figure 4 clearly spots various cluster boundaries in the Indian Map with the percentage prevalence of infections based on the information collected from survey in 2015.

Figure 5. Seasonal Impacts

Survey, Analysis and Results:

With the help of the information collected from the above methods I analysed the scenario. The survey gives a clear picture about the burden exerted by STH in various sites of India. More than 50% of the surveyed population were rural based.

Nutritional Data: Every individual surveyed was nutritionally active as per the Body Mass Index values calculated from their Height and weight numerical provided by them. $BMI = \frac{kg}{m^2}$ where kg is a person's weight in kilograms and m^2 is their height in metres squared. The mean height obtained was 1.50m. The mean weight obtained was 55.1kg. Mean $BMI = \frac{55.1kg}{1.50m^2} = 24.5$, this indicates the normal body mass index.

Types of latrines used have a mass effect on the multiplication of infections. As per the statistics provided by UNICEF in July 01, 2021 it states that 1% of

Urban and 22% of rural population defecates in the open area [6]. From my survey I understood that India is moving a great way ahead to become open Defecation free because almost 60% of population is using flush latrines and the remaining pit and ventilated.

Source of drinking water was found to be a night mare serving as a reservoir of cysts and larvae of STH incubating them for the spread of infections. 28.4% people from Rural areas used untreated river water for drinking and household purposes. Human or animal waste can enter the water through different ways, including sewage overflows, sewage systems that are not working properly, polluted storm water runoff, and agricultural runoff. This happens mostly in Agricultural areas.

Seasonal Impacts: Parasitism is expanding to the greater scale during the wet season and the graph declines during the dry season. [Fig.5]

Most of them being asymptomatic they remain a carrier of helminths. The numbers of cases registered in the hospitals were relatively low as per the data collected from health care workers. *Ascaris lumbricoides* is the most threatening causative agent in the rural area

and increasing prevalence of *Trichuris trichiura* and *Ancylostoma duodenale* in the urban population [7]. From the survey conducted 53.5% infections were caused by *A. lumbricoides*.

Overview of Survey:	
<i>No. of Children</i>	91
<i>No. of Adults</i>	109
Parasite Species Involved:	
<i>A. Lumbricoides</i>	85
<i>T. trichiura</i>	1
<i>N. americanus</i>	13
<i>A. duodenale</i>	
<i>Unknown</i>	60
Examination Method	
<i>Stool Examination</i>	90
<i>Serological test</i>	33
<i>Colonoscopy</i>	2
<i>Never performed any tests</i>	75
Infection period	
<i>Days</i>	47.7%
<i>Weeks</i>	40.08%
<i>Months</i>	10%
<i>Years</i>	1.5%
Medications Used:	
<i>Albendazole</i>	63.7%
<i>Mebendazole</i>	25.2%
<i>Piperazine</i>	3%
<i>Ivermectin</i>	8.1%

Figure 6: This summarizes the key numerical determined from the survey.

The common symptoms revealed were: Diarrhoea, Loss of appetite, Abdominal Pain, Impaired physical and cognitive development, Blood and protein loss, Rectal Prolapses, Weakness and Worms or blood in stool. The Primary health care workers during the interview explained the complications which are stunting the growth and physical development of children i.e. worms feed on blood and tissues of intestines leading to mal-absorption and anaemia. Especially the round worms compete for Vitamin A in the intestine causing nutritional deficit.

The study also clearly indicates the usage of Anthelmintics either annually or biannually depending on the prevalence of Helminthiasis. The drugs administered commonly are Albendazole, Mebendazole, Ivermectin, and Praziquantel. In order to eliminate STH other strategies are implemented such as vaccination, Mass drug administration, vector control, proper water sanitation and Hygiene methods [WASH] and Awareness programmes in School level.

Conclusion

This study interprets that India has accelerating cases of STH globally as per the statistics of WHO. The highest prevalence occurs to areas where sanitation is inadequate and water supplies are unsafe. Children and pregnant women are more vulnerable to such infections due to the wide prevalence of vectors in the environment, and the probability of re-infections is also very high due to increased penetration via faecal-oral

route. The Indian Government has initiated two missions 1] The Swachh Bharat – for universal sanitation coverage, 2] The fixed day Anganwadi and school National Deworming day since 2015 for the mass drug administration to control worm infections in children. The survey stipulates the necessity of improved sanitation in rural areas as the literature indicates most of the cases are from them. This study provides adequately sufficient knowledge to understand the burden of helminthic infections in India.

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